

D2.3 Workshop proceedings

Workshop on single-molecule protein folding 03/2023 in Antholz, Italy

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (CasProt)**
No. 952333

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Deliverable No:	D2.3
Work package no. and title	WP2 - Workshops, training, and symposia
Task no. and title:	Task 2.3.: Interim workshops
Nature:	Report
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead Beneficiary:	UPJS
Author(s):	Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.
Date of publication:	31 st of March 2023

Document History

Date	Author	Version
March 30, 2023		d1

APPROVALS

Task leader: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.

WP leader: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.

Project coordinator: Assoc. Prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Single Molecule Folding Workshop took place from the 13th to the 17th of March 2023 and was organized as a joint event by Pavol Jozef Safarik University in Kosice, Slovakia (UPJS) and Technical University of Munich, Germany (TUM) in Antholz, Italy. The workshop aimed to bring together experts in the field to discuss various topics and aspects related to single-molecule protein folding. As outlined in the initial project proposal, the workshop sought to facilitate the exchange of ideas and foster collaboration among participants. This was achieved through a combination of selective interim workshops and plenary conferences that encouraged networking among attendees. The 5-day workshop was dedicated to discussing the latest advancements in single-molecule protein folding research and applied areas. Participants included partners from the organizing institutions as well as invited specialists from external organizations. The discussions covered recent prospects and perspectives in single-molecule protein biophysics, with a particular focus on advancements in related instrumentation and scientific areas. Key topics explored during the workshop included interactions within biological systems, protein-protein mechanics, and the construction and design of optical tweezers and microfluidic devices. These discussions aimed to deepen participants' understanding of single-molecule protein folding, as well as to address the fundamental aspects of protein-protein interactions and instrument design.

Overall, the Single Molecule Folding Workshop was a successful event that helped to enhance collaboration among participants, share valuable insights, and further advance the field of single-molecule protein folding. Through the exchange of ideas and networking opportunities provided, attendees were able to gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter and contribute to the development of cutting-edge research in this area.

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1. INTRODUCTION: PROGRAM

Winter School 2023 — Antholz					
CasProt	Monday 13 th March	Tuesday 14 th March	Wednesday 15 th March	Thursday 16 th March	Friday 17 th March
	Workshops E27 & Workshops E22				
08:45–09:30		Samuel Randriamanantsoa	Fabian Engbrecht	Iris Ruider	Sophie Kurzbach
			Mihai Bodescu	Andreas Walbrun	Daniel Bublitz
09:30–10:15		Franz Hutterer	Benedikt Mairhörmann	Arsenii Hordeichyk	Revanth Coimbatore Varadarajan
			Katharina Augustin	Carina Wrobel	Adina Hausch
10:15–10:30	Break				
10:30–11:15		Ania Pastucha	Francesco Padovani	Caro Heiler	Florian Stratmann
			Veronika Džupponová		
11:15–12:00		Marion Raich	Sandra Andrusca	Lukas Neumann	
	<i>München → Antholz</i>	Lunch and Group Activities			<i>Antholz → München</i>
18:00–19:30	Dinner				
	Evening Talks & Stand-up Comedy				
Session Chair		Daphné Vannier	Timon Nast-Kolb	Ania Pastucha	
20:00–20:25	Welcome and Organization Andreas Bausch	Chiao-Peng Hsu	Mandana Hadawi	Andreas Bausch & Matthias Rief	
20:25–20:50		Suji Choi	Daphné Vannier	Gabriel Zoldak	
		Break			
21:00–21:25		Kurt Schmoller	Benedikt Mairhörmann	Michal Gala	
21:25–21:50		Yagya Chadha	Alissa Finster	Timon Nast-Kolb	

The Single Molecule Folding Workshop was a five-day event designed to bring together experts and researchers in the field of single-molecule protein folding. The comprehensive program included presentations, discussions, and networking opportunities to promote knowledge exchange and foster collaborations among participants.

Day 1: The workshop commenced with an opening ceremony that welcomed attendees and introduced the event's objectives. Following this, the first session featured keynote presentations from renowned expert in the biomedical field - Prof. Andreas Bausch, providing an overview of the current state of the application of the protein research, challenges faced, and potential future directions.

Day 2: The second day was dedicated to the development and application of cutting-edge technologies, including optical tweezers and microfluidic devices. Researchers and engineers shared their experiences in designing, constructing, and using these tools for single-molecule protein folding studies.

Day 3: On the third day, the workshop turned its attention to biochemistry of protein-protein interactions, an essential aspect of protein folding. Experts in this area presented their latest findings and shared insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying chaperone-assisted folding. Additionally, participants engaged in a roundtable discussion, exploring the potential applications of chaperone research in biotechnology and medicine. Presentations covered topics

such as the role of proteins in force generation. An interactive session allowed researchers to showcase their work and receive feedback from their peers.

Day 4: The fourth day of the workshop dealt with bioinformatics and theoretical evolutionary aspects fo protein folding.

Day 5: The final day of the workshop focused on interdisciplinary discussions and future perspectives. Researchers from various fields, such as computational biology and biophysics, presented their work on data analysis and the development of new experimental techniques. The event concluded with a summarising session highlighting the key findings and insights from the workshop, along with a discussion on potential avenues for future research and collaborations.

The Workshop aimed to promote a deeper understanding of single-molecule protein folding and facilitate collaboration among experts in the field. The diverse program ensured that a wide range of topics was covered, from fundamental research to practical applications, making the event an enriching and valuable experience for all attendees.

Fig.1. CasProt Workshop participants

2. DESCRIPTION OF WORKSHOPS RELATED TO SINGLE-MOLECULE FOLDING

	Workshops
Samuel Randriamanantsoa	Are statistics done terribly wrong?
Marion Raich	Analysis of fluorescent data in python
Ania Pastucha	Introduction to Arivis analysis
Franz Hutterer	Proper Data Acquisition, Storage and Maintenance
Fabian Englbrecht	Using Chat-GPT in research
Benedikt Mairhörmann	Transfer learning for cell segmentation with cellpose
Francesco Padovani	How to make AI models accessible to the end user with Python
Sandra Andrusca	Bioinformatics
Mihai Bodescu	Optical Trapping
Katharina Augustin	Biochemistry for Physicists
Veronika Džupponová	Role of disulfide bonds in pathological human light chains IgG instability
Iris Ruider	Parallelization and Linux Cluster to deal with big data
Arsenii Hordeichyk	Phase separation of reconstituted focal adhesions
Caro Heiler	CRISPR and beyond
Lukas Neumann	Bilayer patterning methods
Andreas Walbrun	Data Analysis (Constant Distance, HMM, Rates, ...)
Carina Wrobel	Protein Purification - Soluble vs. Membrane Proteins
Sophie Kurzbach	Applications of softlithographically generated devices
Revanth Coimbatore Varadarajan	Possibilities and limitations of microfluidic device design and production
Florian Stratmann	Photomask design / 3D body design with CorelCAD with hands-on exercises
Daniel Bublitz	Fluorescence Measurements with the C-Trap
Adina Hausch	Physics for Biochemists (WLC, Fitting, force distributions, PSD, trap crosstalk)

2.1 Are statistics [on single molecule data] done terribly wrong?

Statistics play a crucial role in our understanding of the world [1]. They are used to inform decisions, shape policies, and contribute to the advancement of scientific research. However, the misuse or misinterpretation of statistical data can lead to false conclusions and potentially harmful consequences. This raises the question: are statistics done terribly wrong? In this talk, we examined the common pitfalls and misconceptions related to statistics and discuss ways to improve statistical literacy and practice. One common issue with statistics is the misuse or misinterpretation of the data. Often, this is a result of people not having a thorough understanding of statistical concepts, leading them to draw incorrect conclusions or overstate the significance of certain findings. For instance, confusing correlation with causation is a common mistake. Just because two variables appear to be related does not necessarily mean that one causes the other. It is essential to consider other factors and potential confounding variables that could explain the observed relationship. Another issue is the concept of statistical significance. Statistical significance is a measure of the likelihood that a particular result is due to chance. However, it is

often misinterpreted as an indicator of practical or scientific importance. A statistically significant result may not necessarily be practically significant, and conversely, a non-significant result may still hold practical importance. Moreover, the problem of multiple comparisons arises when researchers perform numerous statistical tests on the same dataset. This can increase the likelihood of false positives or false negatives. To avoid this, researchers must correct for multiple comparisons, but this is not always done or reported in the literature, leading to potentially flawed conclusions. Another aspect of statistical analysis that can lead to errors is the presence of bias and confounding factors. Bias can be introduced at various stages of a study, such as during data collection, analysis, or interpretation. For example, selection bias occurs when the sample used in a study is not representative of the target population. This can lead to results that are not generalizable to the broader population. Confounding factors are variables that are related to both the independent and dependent variables in a study and can lead to spurious correlations. If not accounted for, confounding factors can cause researchers to falsely attribute the observed relationship to the independent variable, when in fact, the confounding variable is the actual cause. To address the issues of misuse and misinterpretation of statistics, it is essential to improve statistical literacy among the general public, policymakers, and researchers. This involves educating individuals about the fundamental principles of statistics, such as understanding the difference between correlation and causation, recognizing the limitations of statistical significance, and being aware of the risks of multiple comparisons. Moreover, researchers must adhere to best practices in statistical analysis, which includes properly accounting for bias and confounding factors, correcting for multiple comparisons, and being transparent in reporting their methodology and results. By following these guidelines, researchers can minimize errors and increase the reliability of their findings. Peer review also plays a crucial role in ensuring the accuracy and validity of statistical analyses. By having other experts in the field review and critique research findings, potential errors and biases can be identified and addressed before they are published and disseminated to the public.

In conclusion, while statistics can be a powerful tool for understanding the single-molecule folding, it is essential to recognize the potential pitfalls and misconceptions that can arise when using and interpreting statistical data. By improving statistical literacy, adhering to best practices, and promoting rigorous peer review, we can minimize the risk of doing statistics terribly wrong and enhance the reliability and validity of statistical findings.

2.2 Analysis of fluorescent data in python

Single-molecule folding studies provide valuable insights into the complex mechanisms governing protein folding and conformational changes [2]. Fluorescence techniques, such as Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET), have emerged as powerful tools for investigating these processes at the single-molecule level. In combination with the versatile programming language Python, researchers can efficiently analyze the vast amounts of data generated by fluorescence experiments to better understand protein folding dynamics. This talk discussed the use of fluorescence techniques in single-molecule folding studies and the application of Python for data

analysis. Fluorescence-based techniques offer several advantages for single-molecule folding studies, including high sensitivity, non-invasive measurements, and real-time monitoring of conformational changes. One widely used method is FRET, which relies on the energy transfer between a donor fluorophore and an acceptor fluorophore attached to specific sites on the protein of interest. As the distance between the fluorophores changes during protein folding, the efficiency of energy transfer varies, providing information about the conformational dynamics of the protein. By analyzing the changes in fluorescence intensity or lifetime, researchers can gain insights into the folding pathways, intermediates, and kinetics of individual protein molecules. Additionally, by employing techniques such as alternating laser excitation (ALEX), researchers can simultaneously monitor multiple fluorescence signals, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay of molecular interactions and conformational changes.

Python is a versatile and widely used programming language that offers numerous advantages for analyzing fluorescence data from single-molecule folding experiments. With its extensive library of scientific packages, such as NumPy, SciPy, and pandas, Python provides powerful tools for processing and analyzing large datasets, as well as visualizing results using packages like Matplotlib and Seaborn. To analyze single-molecule folding data using Python, researchers typically perform the following steps: 1. data preprocessing: Raw fluorescence data must first be processed to remove noise and artifacts. This may involve techniques such as baseline correction, filtering, or normalization, 2. feature extraction: After preprocessing, researchers must extract relevant features from the fluorescence data, such as the FRET efficiency or changes in fluorescence intensity, that are indicative of protein conformational changes, 3. data analysis: Researchers can then apply various statistical and computational methods to analyze the extracted features, such as fitting kinetic models, clustering algorithms, or machine learning techniques to identify folding pathways, intermediates, and rates, 4. visualization: Python's visualization libraries facilitate the creation of informative plots and graphs to represent the results of the data analysis, enabling researchers to better interpret their findings and communicate them to others.

Fluorescence techniques, particularly FRET, have proven invaluable for single-molecule folding studies by providing real-time, sensitive measurements of protein conformational dynamics. The Python programming language, with its extensive ecosystem of scientific packages, offers researchers a powerful and versatile platform for analyzing the large and complex datasets generated by these experiments. By harnessing the capabilities of both fluorescence techniques and Python for data analysis, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the molecular mechanisms governing protein folding and potentially inform the development of novel therapeutic strategies targeting protein misfolding and aggregation-related diseases.

2.3 Proper data acquisition

Single-molecule folding studies have revolutionized our understanding of protein folding mechanisms and dynamics by allowing researchers to probe the behavior of individual molecules [3]. Obtaining accurate and reliable data from these experiments is crucial for drawing meaningful

conclusions and advancing our knowledge of protein folding processes. This talk discussed the essential steps and considerations for proper single-molecule folding data acquisition, including sample preparation, experimental setup, and data collection. The choice of experimental technique and instrumentation is essential for acquiring accurate and reliable single-molecule folding data. The following factors should be considered: technique selection and instrument optimisation.

Various techniques can be employed for single-molecule folding studies, including fluorescence-based methods (e.g., FRET, confocal microscopy), force spectroscopy (e.g., optical tweezers, atomic force microscopy), and single-molecule imaging (e.g., total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy). The choice of technique depends on the specific research question and the desired level of spatial and temporal resolution. The chosen instrument must be calibrated and optimized to ensure accurate measurements and minimize experimental artifacts. This may involve aligning optical components, setting laser power, adjusting detector sensitivity, or optimizing the force applied in force spectroscopy experiments. Proper data collection is crucial for obtaining reliable and interpretable single-molecule folding data. Consider the following aspects during data collection: 1. Signal-to-noise ratio: The experimental conditions should be optimized to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio, which will improve the accuracy and precision of the measurements. This can involve adjusting laser power, detector sensitivity, or exposure times. 2. Data acquisition parameters: The choice of data acquisition parameters, such as sampling rate and acquisition time, should be carefully considered based on the expected folding dynamics and the temporal resolution of the technique. Acquiring data at an appropriate rate will ensure sufficient sampling of the folding events while avoiding excessive data storage and processing requirements. 3. Replicates and controls: To ensure the robustness and reproducibility of the results, multiple replicates should be performed, and appropriate controls (e.g., labeled and unlabeled samples, denatured proteins) should be included to account for potential artifacts or background signals. Proper single-molecule folding data acquisition is essential for obtaining accurate and reliable insights into protein folding dynamics. By carefully considering sample preparation, experimental setup, and data collection parameters, researchers can ensure the quality and interpretability of the data and advance our understanding of the complex processes governing protein folding at the single-molecule level.

2.4 Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics is an interdisciplinary field that combines computer science, statistics, and biology to analyze and interpret complex biological data. In recent years, bioinformatics has emerged as a powerful tool for understanding protein folding dynamics, particularly in the context of single-molecule folding and localisation studies [4]. This talk discussed the role of bioinformatics in single-molecule folding research and its potential to advance our understanding of protein folding mechanisms and dynamics. Bioinformatics plays a crucial role in various aspects of single-molecule folding research, including data analysis, modeling, and prediction. Single-molecule folding experiments generate large amounts of data, often in the form of time-resolved

fluorescence signals or force-extension curves. Bioinformatics tools and algorithms can be employed to preprocess and analyze these data, extracting relevant features (e.g., FRET efficiency, unfolding forces) and identifying patterns or trends that reveal information about protein folding dynamics and pathways. Computational methods, such as molecular dynamics simulations, can be used to model protein folding at the atomic level, providing detailed insights into the forces and interactions driving folding events. By integrating experimental data from single-molecule folding studies, researchers can refine and validate these models, leading to a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of protein folding mechanisms. Bioinformatics approaches, such as machine learning and network-based methods, can be used to predict protein folding pathways and identify folding intermediates from experimental data. These predictions can help guide further experimental studies and uncover novel folding mechanisms or regulatory factors.

Bioinformatics has the potential to significantly advance our understanding of protein folding at the single-molecule level. By providing powerful tools for data analysis, modeling, and prediction, bioinformatics can complement experimental approaches and help researchers uncover the complex and often heterogeneous mechanisms governing protein folding. Furthermore, the integration of bioinformatics with single-molecule folding studies can facilitate the identification of folding determinants, such as sequence and structural features, that can inform the rational design of proteins with desired folding properties or functions.

2.5 Optical trapping

Optical trapping, also known as optical tweezers, is a powerful technique for studying protein folding at the single-molecule level [3]. It allows researchers to manipulate and measure forces acting on individual biomolecules with high precision and sensitivity, providing unprecedented insights into the folding dynamics and mechanisms of proteins. This talk discussed the principles of optical trapping, its applications in single-molecule folding studies, and the unique advantages and challenges of this technique. Optical trapping relies on the principle of light-induced forces to trap and manipulate small particles, such as biomolecules or polystyrene beads. When a focused laser beam interacts with a particle, it exerts forces that can trap the particle at the focus of the beam. These forces include the gradient force, which attracts the particle toward the high-intensity region of the beam, and the scattering force, which pushes the particle along the direction of the light propagation. By carefully controlling the laser beam properties, researchers can stably trap particles and apply controlled forces to manipulate them. Optical trapping has found numerous applications in the field of single-molecule folding research, enabling the study of protein folding dynamics under various conditions and applied forces.

Optical tweezers can be used to apply mechanical forces to individual protein molecules, either by stretching or compressing them, to study their folding and unfolding dynamics. By measuring the force-extension relationship of a protein, researchers can gain insights into its folding landscape, energy barriers, and intermediate states.

Optical trapping enables the real-time monitoring of protein folding kinetics by measuring the changes in extension or force as a function of time. By varying the applied force or pulling rate, researchers can probe the protein folding dynamics over a wide range of timescales, from microseconds to seconds or longer. Optical tweezers can be used to study protein-protein interactions, such as chaperone-assisted folding, by manipulating one or both interacting partners and measuring the forces required for their association or dissociation. This can provide valuable information about the energetics and kinetics of protein-protein interactions, as well as the role of chaperones in facilitating protein folding.

Optical trapping offers several unique advantages for single-molecule folding research, including:

- High force resolution and sensitivity: Optical tweezers can exert and measure forces with piconewton (pN) sensitivity, allowing researchers to probe the subtle forces governing protein folding and unfolding.
- Wide force range: Optical trapping can apply forces over a broad range, from a few piconewtons to hundreds of piconewtons, enabling the study of protein folding under various mechanical constraints.
- Non-invasive manipulation: Unlike other force spectroscopy techniques, such as atomic force microscopy, optical trapping does not involve direct physical contact with the sample, minimizing potential damage or perturbations to the protein.
- Real-time measurements: Optical tweezers allow for real-time monitoring of protein folding dynamics, providing a detailed picture of the folding process and enabling the identification of transient intermediates and rare events.

Despite its numerous advantages, optical trapping also presents some challenges for single-molecule folding studies. The analysis of force-extension curves and folding kinetics obtained from optical tweezers experiments can be complex, requiring sophisticated statistical and computational methods to extract meaningful information about the folding landscape and kinetics. In addition, protein samples must be specifically prepared for optical trapping experiments, typically involving the attachment of the protein to beads which can be very tedious.

2.6 Biochemistry for Physicist

The goal of a talk entitled "Biochemistry for Physicists" was to provide physicists with a foundational understanding of biochemistry and demonstrate the value of interdisciplinary collaboration between the two fields. By bridging the gap between physics and biochemistry, researchers can leverage the strengths of both disciplines to address complex biological problems and advance our understanding of the molecular basis of life.

2.7 Physics for Biochemist

The aim of such a talk would be to introduce biochemists to the fundamental concepts and principles of physics and to highlight the potential areas of interdisciplinary collaboration between the two fields.

2.8 Fluorescent Measurements with the C-trap

The C-trap, developed by Lumicks, is an advanced biophysical instrument that combines optical tweezers, confocal microscopy, and microfluidics in a single platform. This integrated approach allows researchers to manipulate, visualize, and study biomolecules at the single-molecule level with high spatial and temporal resolution. In this talk, we focused on the fluorescent measurements aspect of the C-trap and its applications in single-molecule biophysics research. The C-trap's confocal microscopy component enables researchers to perform high-resolution fluorescent measurements on single biomolecules [5]. The confocal microscope employs a laser to excite fluorophores attached to the biomolecules of interest, and the emitted fluorescence is then collected through a high-numerical-aperture objective. A pinhole in the detection path spatially filters the emitted light, allowing for the visualization of a single focal plane and improving the signal-to-noise ratio. The C-trap is equipped with multiple laser lines, enabling the excitation of various fluorophores, such as green fluorescent protein (GFP), Alexa Fluor dyes, and quantum dots. This capability allows researchers to perform multicolor fluorescence experiments, which can be used to study interactions between different biomolecules or to monitor conformational changes within a single molecule. The combination of fluorescence measurements with optical tweezers and microfluidics in the C-trap offers unique opportunities for single-molecule biophysics research. Some key applications include FRET. Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) measurements: By attaching donor and acceptor fluorophores to specific locations within a biomolecule, researchers can use FRET to monitor conformational changes or protein-protein interactions at the single-molecule level. The C-trap's confocal microscopy component enables the detection of FRET signals with high sensitivity and temporal resolution. Next, fluorescent measurements in the C-trap can be used to monitor the folding and unfolding dynamics of single protein molecules in real-time. By combining these measurements with optical tweezers, researchers can apply mechanical forces to the protein and directly visualize the resulting conformational changes. The C-trap's multicolor fluorescence capabilities enable the study of interactions between different biomolecules, such as the binding of transcription factors to DNA or the assembly of protein complexes. By combining fluorescence measurements with optical tweezers, researchers can apply forces to the interacting partners and study the effects on their binding and dissociation kinetics. The C-trap can be used to monitor the activity of single enzyme molecules by tracking the fluorescence signal from fluorophore-labeled substrates or products. This can provide valuable insights into the catalytic mechanisms and kinetics of enzymes at the single-molecule level.

The C-trap developed by Lumicks at TUM (see Fig. 2) offers a powerful platform for single-molecule biophysics research, combining optical tweezers, confocal microscopy, and

microfluidics. Fluorescent measurements in the C-trap enable the visualization and study of biomolecular interactions, conformational changes, and enzymatic activity with high sensitivity and temporal resolution. This integrated approach has the potential to provide unprecedented insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying biological processes at the single-molecule level.

Fig. 2. LUMICKS C-trap at TU Munich (<https://lumicks.com/c-trap-installed-at-technical-university-of-munich/>)

3. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF SOME OF THE EVENING TALKS

	Evening talks
Chiao-Peng Hsu	Soft matter evolution and revolution
Suji Choi	Printing Fiber-Infused Gel scaffolds to Build In Vitro Ventricle Models with Cellular Alignment
Kurt Schmoller	Histone homeostasis in different nutrients
Yagya Chadha	Budding Yeast Cell Size Control in Dynamic Nutrient Conditions
Mandana Hadawi	Introducing Lipids Nanodiscs in Force Spectroscopy to Investigate the Talin/Integrin-Complex
Daphné Vannier	Stem cells and vascularization
Benedikt Mairhörmann	Identifying cell-cycle control mechanisms by high-throughput phenotyping on a single-cell level
Alissa Finster	Cell-volume-dependency of mitochondrial DNA in budding yeast
Gabriel Zoldak	Life in a widening country: from the establishment of Cassovia New Industry Cluster to the application for HE scheme Teaming for Excellence
Michal Gala	Bioinformatics analysis of 3D protein structure and transcriptomics data
Timon Nast-Kolb	Nematode nematics

3.1 Soft matter evolution and revolution

Soft matter science, which encompasses the study of a diverse range of materials such as polymers, colloids, gels, and liquid crystals, has undergone significant evolution and revolution over the past few decades. This talk explored the key milestones, breakthroughs, and emerging trends in soft matter science, highlighting the multidisciplinary approach that has led to novel applications and a deeper understanding of these fascinating materials, e.g. [6-7].

Soft matter science is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the study of materials with complex and dynamic properties, including polymers, colloids, gels, and liquid crystals. These materials are characterized by their ability to respond to external stimuli, self-assemble, and exhibit unique mechanical and structural properties. The evolution and revolution of soft matter science has been driven by advancements in theoretical understanding, experimental techniques, and computational methods. The foundations of soft matter science can be traced back to the early 20th century when pioneering researchers like Pierre-Gilles de Gennes and Sir Sam Edwards laid the groundwork for understanding the behavior of polymers, liquid crystals, and colloidal systems. These early discoveries paved the way for a more comprehensive understanding of soft matter physics and chemistry. Significant progress in soft matter theory has helped to unravel the complexities of soft materials. Key developments include the Flory-Huggins theory for polymer solutions, the Onsager theory for liquid crystal phase transitions, and the Derjaguin-Landau-Verwey-Overbeek (DLVO) theory for colloidal stability. These theoretical frameworks have provided crucial insights into the thermodynamics, phase behavior, and stability of soft matter systems. Computational methods, such as molecular dynamics simulations and Monte Carlo techniques, have greatly facilitated the study of soft matter systems. The development of coarse-grained models has allowed for the investigation of complex phenomena, such as self-assembly, over longer timescales and larger length scales than previously possible. Soft matter science has found numerous applications in diverse fields, such as biotechnology, nanotechnology, and materials science. Examples include the development of stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems, self-healing materials, and advanced displays based on liquid crystals. The emergence of active matter, which includes self-propelled particles and living systems, has opened up new frontiers in

soft matter research. The evolution and revolution of soft matter science have transformed our understanding of these fascinating materials and their properties. The multidisciplinary approach, combining theoretical, experimental, and computational methods, has led to significant breakthroughs and novel applications. As soft matter science continues to advance, we can expect further discoveries and innovations in the coming years.

3.2 Introducing lipid nanodiscs in force spectroscopy to investigate talin/integrin complex

This talk introduced the use of lipid nanodiscs in force spectroscopy to investigate the talin/integrin complex, a critical component of cell adhesion and mechanotransduction. By incorporating lipid nanodiscs, force spectroscopy can provide a more native-like membrane environment for studying the dynamics and interactions of the talin/integrin complex [8], leading to a better understanding of cell adhesion and signaling processes. The talin/integrin complex plays a crucial role in cell adhesion, migration, and mechanotransduction. Investigating the molecular interactions and mechanical properties of this complex is essential for understanding cellular processes and developing potential therapeutic targets. Force spectroscopy has emerged as a powerful tool to study these interactions at the single-molecule level [3]. Integrating lipid nanodiscs in force spectroscopy experiments can provide a more physiologically relevant environment to study the talin/integrin complex. Talins are adaptor proteins that bind to integrins, transmembrane receptors that mediate cell-cell and cell-extracellular matrix adhesion. The interaction between talin and integrin is essential for the activation and regulation of integrin, which plays a pivotal role in cellular processes such as cell migration, differentiation, and mechanotransduction. Understanding the dynamics of this complex is critical to comprehending cell adhesion and signaling mechanisms. Force spectroscopy is a powerful technique that allows researchers to measure the forces involved in molecular interactions at the single-molecule level. This method uses an atomic force microscope (AFM) or optical tweezers to manipulate individual molecules, enabling the investigation of molecular interactions, mechanical properties, and unfolding pathways. Force spectroscopy has been widely used to study protein-protein, protein-ligand, and protein-DNA interactions. Lipid nanodiscs are nanoscale, discoidal patches of lipid bilayer surrounded by a belt of membrane scaffold proteins [9]. They offer a native-like environment for the solubilization and study of membrane proteins, including receptors, channels, and transporters. Lipid nanodiscs enable researchers to study membrane proteins in a controlled lipid environment without detergents or artificial liposomes, providing a more physiologically relevant context.

Incorporating lipid nanodiscs in force spectroscopy experiments can provide a more native-like membrane environment for studying the talin/integrin complex. This approach enables the investigation of talin/integrin interactions and the effects of membrane composition on these interactions, ultimately leading to a better understanding of cell adhesion and signaling processes. Additionally, lipid nanodiscs allow for incorporating other membrane proteins, such as integrin-

associated proteins, which can be essential for understanding the regulation and function of the talin/integrin complex in a cellular context.

Lipid nanodiscs offer a promising approach to studying the talin/integrin complex in force spectroscopy experiments by providing a more physiologically relevant environment. This integration can lead to a deeper understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying cell adhesion, migration, and mechanotransduction. Further development and application of this technique will contribute to our knowledge of the talin/integrin complex and may facilitate the development of novel therapeutic strategies targeting these essential cellular processes.

3.3 Bioinformatics analysis of 3D structure and transcriptomics data

The integration of bioinformatics analysis of 3D structural data with transcriptomics data provides a powerful approach to understanding complex biological systems [10-13]. This talk discussed the importance of combining these two data types and highlights various bioinformatics tools and methods for integrating 3D structural and transcriptomics data to gain insights into protein function, gene regulation, and cellular processes. The understanding of complex biological systems requires the integration of diverse types of data, such as 3D structural data and transcriptomics data. Bioinformatics plays a crucial role in the analysis, integration, and interpretation of these data sets, providing insights into protein structure, function, and interactions, as well as gene expression, regulation, and cellular processes. This talk discussed the significance of combining 3D structural and transcriptomics data and the various bioinformatics tools and methods used for their analysis.

Three-dimensional (3D) structural data provide detailed information on the spatial arrangement of atoms within macromolecules, such as proteins, nucleic acids, and their complexes. Understanding the 3D structure of these macromolecules is essential for determining their function, predicting their interactions, and designing drugs that target specific proteins or nucleic acids. Methods such as X-ray crystallography, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) are commonly used to determine the 3D structures of biological macromolecules. Transcriptomics is the study of the complete set of RNA transcripts produced by a cell, tissue, or organism under specific conditions. Transcriptomics data provides insights into gene expression patterns, regulation, and cellular processes. High-throughput techniques, such as RNA sequencing (RNA-Seq), have revolutionized the field of transcriptomics, enabling the generation of large-scale gene expression data sets for various biological systems and conditions. The integration of 3D structural and transcriptomics data can lead to a deeper understanding of biological systems. For example, transcriptomics data can provide information on the expression levels of specific genes or proteins under various conditions, while 3D structural data can reveal the molecular mechanisms of protein function and interactions. By combining these data types, researchers can gain insights into how changes in gene expression are linked to changes in protein structure and function, ultimately elucidating the complex interplay between structure, function, and regulation in biological systems.

Various bioinformatics tools and methods have been developed to analyze and integrate 3D structural and transcriptomics data. Tools such as PyMOL, UCSF Chimera, and VMD can be used

to visualize and analyze 3D structures of proteins and nucleic acids. Databases such as STRING and BioGRID provide information on experimentally validated and predicted PPIs. At the same time, tools like Cytoscape can be used to visualize and analyze protein interaction networks in the context of gene expression data. Tools like DESeq2, edgeR, and limma can be used to analyze differential gene expression from RNA-Seq data. In contrast, tools like GSEA and DAVID can be used for functional enrichment analysis to identify biological processes associated with differentially expressed genes—platforms like Bio3D, Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV), and Genome3D.

3.4 Nematode nematics

Nematode nematics is an interdisciplinary field that explores the relationship between nematode behavior and liquid crystal physics [14-15]. This talk discussed the unique characteristics of nematodes that allow them to exhibit nematic behavior, the role of liquid crystal physics in understanding nematode organization, and the potential applications of nematode nematics in the development of novel materials and biophysical research tools. Nematodes, or roundworms, are a diverse group of microscopic organisms found in various environments, including soil, water, and even within other organisms as parasites. Interestingly, some nematodes have been observed to exhibit nematic behavior, which refers to the alignment and organization of particles in a way that resembles the properties of liquid crystals. Nematode nematics is a burgeoning field of study that combines the principles of liquid crystal physics with the investigation of nematode behavior and organization.

Nematodes possess certain characteristics that make them suitable for exhibiting nematic behavior. They have elongated, cylindrical bodies with a high aspect ratio, making their alignment and orientation similar to that of rod-like particles in liquid crystal systems. Additionally, nematodes are highly motile, and their locomotion can lead to the emergence of collective behavior and self-organization, reminiscent of the orientational order observed in liquid crystals. The study of nematode nematics utilizes the principles of liquid crystal physics to describe and understand the organization and behavior of nematode populations. In nematic liquid crystals, rod-like particles align along a common direction, known as the director, without maintaining long-range positional order. Similarly, nematodes in a nematic phase exhibit a preferred orientation, leading to the formation of aligned structures or patterns. By applying liquid crystal theory, researchers can develop mathematical models and simulations to investigate the factors influencing nematode organization and predict their behavior under various conditions. The study of nematode nematics holds promise for several potential applications. Understanding the principles governing nematode nematics could inspire the design of new materials that exhibit similar self-organization and alignment properties. These materials could have potential applications in optics, electronics, and sensing technologies. Nematode nematics could serve as a model system for investigating the collective behavior of living organisms, providing insights into the principles governing self-organization, pattern formation, and alignment in biological systems. Since nematodes are sensitive to their surroundings and exhibit changes in behavior and

organization in response to environmental factors, nematode nematics could be employed as a bioindicator for assessing soil and water quality.

Nematode nematics represent an exciting interdisciplinary field that merges the principles of liquid crystal physics with the study of nematode behavior and organization. By investigating the factors that govern nematode alignment and self-organization, researchers can gain insights into the collective behavior of living organisms and potentially develop novel materials and biophysical research tools. As the field advances, nematode nematics may uncover new opportunities and applications in materials science, biophysics, and environmental monitoring.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT TO OTHER GRANTS

This publication is also the result of the project implementation: Development of nanosensory photonic systems for rapid virus detection using methods of controlled evolution of protein platforms: the case of SARS-CoV-2 acronym BioPickmol, ITMS2014+: 313011AUW6 supported by the Operational Programme Integrated Infrastructure, funded by the ERDF“

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